

Genetic nature of leaf epicuticular wax (EW) content in rice

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Leaf EW content has been related to drought resistance in sorghum, wheat, barley, soybean, and maize. EW content in rice leaves increases cuticular resistance to transpiration, which may confer dehydration tolerance. We studied the genetic nature of EW content in rice leaves in 1988-89.

Leaf EW of phytotron-grown plants was extracted with chloroform, the chloroform evaporated off with N₂ gas, and EW reconstituted in 3 ml CCl₄. This solution was injected into a gas-liquid chromatograph (GLC). EW content in the solution of each sample was quantified by comparing total area under the three highest GLC peaks per unit leaf area extracted (Fig. 1). These three peaks, corresponding to C₂₉, C₃₃, and C₃₅ hydrocarbons, consistently accounted for almost all the leaf EW.

Eight parents with high or low leaf EW were crossed in all possible ways except

as reciprocals. The F₁ of the diallel set was analyzed by Griffing and Haymen's methods. Two F₂ populations were studied.

Upland parents IAC25, OS4, and IRAT13 had the highest EW levels. These cultivars belong to Glaszmann's isozyme group VI (japonica). General combining ability (GCA) effects were highly significant and specific combining ability (SCA) effects nonsignificant, indicating a predominance of additive genetic variation. Broad- (h^2_b) and

narrow-sense (h^2_n) heritability were 0.77 and 0.62, respectively. IAC25 and OS4 had the highest positive GCA.

Monomodal distributions were observed in both F₂ populations. In IAC25/Salumpikit (Fig. 2), the number of recombinants matching the EW level of either parent was low, implying polygenic inheritance. Broad-sense heritability was 0.36.

Predominance of additive genetic variation for EW content implies that selection to increase leaf EW would be effective. Low heritability and the difficulty in measuring the trait, however, are obstacles to increasing the EW level in improved rainfed lowland cultivars. An additional constraint is that the sources of high EW are upland cultivars, which are difficult to use in rainfed lowland breeding programs. ■

2. Distribution of leaf EW content in the F₂ population of IAC25/Salumpikit and the range, mean, and SE of the mean. Mean EW contents of P₁, P₂, and F₁ were 16.5, 5.9, and 10.5 mg/m², respectively.

Breeding methods

Evaluating S₁ family recurrent selection in a rice population

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Recurrent selection has been used to improve particular traits in breeding populations of cross-pollinating crops. Difficulties in artificial crossing, however, make it difficult to use in self-pollinating crops such as rice.

Genetic male sterility can facilitate crossing during the intermating phase of recurrent selection. We evaluated S₁ family recurrent selection in the composite population CP103 (IR38499) segregating for genetic male sterility. As the S₁ generation segregated for male sterility, we selected S₁-derived S₃ and S₄ lines, which were homozygous for male fertility.

In 1989 wet season (WS), 79 S₁ lines and 46 S₃ lines were grown. In 1990 dry season (DS), 62 S₁ and 34 S₄ lines were grown. S₁ lines were replicated twice and S₃ and S₄ lines four times each season. Agronomic and grain quality traits were measured on 12 hills/plot. Only plots not affected by rats and tungro were included in the analysis. IR36 could not be

1. Representative gas liquid chromatograms of high-wax IRAT13 and low-wax IR5. The numbers on top of each peak are retention time.